

Chromium (III) Heterocomplexes:
Part I. α -Picolinato - and Quinaldinato-bis (biguanidinium)
Chromium (III) Complexes

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α -Picolinato- and quinaldinato-bis(biguanidinium)chromium (III) complex salts (*viz.*, chloride, bromide, iodide, nitrate, sulphate, perchlorate, thiosulphate, oxalate, *d*-camphor-10-sulphonate of picolinato-complex; chloride, nitrate, sulphate and perchlorate of quinaldinato-complex) have been prepared by the action of α -picolinic acid quinaldonic acids respectively on tris(biguanidinium)-chromium (III) salts. All the complexes are paramagnetic ($\mu_{eff} = 3.62-3.86$ B.M.). This and their electronic absorption spectra show that they are octahedral complexes with d^2sp^3 bonding. Very little change has been observed in the $10Dq$ values of the heterocomplexes from that of the tris(biguanidinium)-complex.

Complex compounds of biguanide with chromium (III) were first reported by Rây and coworkers¹⁻³. They observed that the tris(biguanidinium)chromium(III) complex undergoes hydrolysis forming hydroxo-aquobis(biguanidinium)-complex with the elimination of a molecule of biguanide; the hydrolysis proceeds on to the monobiguanide-complex and finally to chromium hydroxide. In a subsequent communication⁴ they reported the formation of dithiocyanatobis(biguanidinium)chromium (III) salts. In this paper we report the α -picolinato- and quinaldinato-bis(biguanidinium)chromium(III) salts, both the picolinate and the quinaldinate ions behaving as monovalent bidentate groups. It may be of interest here to mention that both intensive and extensive investigations on disubstituted bis(biguanidinium)cobalt (III) complexes have been made by Ghosh and Gupta^{5,6} in this laboratory and also by Dutta and Sarkar⁷⁻⁹ in Burdwan. In majority of the cases the complex has been prepared by oxidising four-coordinated bis(biguanidinium)cobalt (II) complex in presence of some other ligand.

In the present investigation, it has been found that tris(biguanidinium)chromium(III) complex, which is otherwise so prone to hydrolysis in aqueous solutions¹, reacts quite smoothly with α -picolinic or quinaldonic acid, when heated on a steam bath, resulting in the replacement of one biguanide group (BigH^+ , where $\text{BigH}^+ = \text{C}_2\text{N}_5\text{H}_7$) with a picolinate ion (pic') or a quinaldinate ion ($\text{quinald}'$), giving rise to the bivalent complex cation $[\text{Cr}(\text{BigH}^+)_2 \text{pic}']^{++}$ or $[\text{Cr}(\text{BigH}^+)_2 \text{quinald}']^{++}$. This replacement could be very easily effected in the sulphate of the tris(biguanidinium)-complex.

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The molar conductance value of $265.8 \text{ ohm}^{-1} \text{ cm}^2$ at 28.5° for both $[\text{Cr}(\text{BigH}^+)_2 \text{pic}']\text{Cl}_2$ and $[\text{Cr}(\text{BigH}^+)_2 \text{quinald}'](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ confirms the bivalency of the cations.

The magnetic moments, reported in Table I, are in good accord with the spin only value for three unpaired electrons, characteristic of trivalent chromium and suggestive of d^2sp^3 bonding in the complex.

TABLE I

Complex	Temp. (°K)	<i>Magnetic Moments</i>		Diamag. corr. ($\times 10^{-6}$)	χ_A ($\times 10^{-6}$)	μ_{eff} (B.M.)
		χ_m ($\times 10^{-6}$)	χ_m ($\times 10^{-6}$)			
1. $[\text{Cr}(\text{BigH}^+)_2 \text{pic}']\text{SO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	292.5	11.992	6097	224	6321	3.86
2. $[\text{Cr}(\text{BigH}^+)_2 \text{quinald}']\text{SO}_4 \cdot 1.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$	304.5	9.28	5099	240	5339	3.62

Spectral behaviour: The electronic absorption data of these complexes along with those of hexaaquochromium(III)-, dichlorotetraaquochromium(III)-, tris(ethylenediamine) chromium(III)- and tris(biguanidinium) chromium(III) ions are given in Table II. The $10Dq$ values have been obtained from the transition ${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$. It is found that the $10Dq$ values of these complexes are much greater than those of $[\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]^{3+}$ and $[\text{CrCl}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]^+$ (but slightly less than that of $[\text{Cr}(\text{en})_3]^{3+}$, thus indicating a greater stability of these complexes. At the same time it appears that the substitution of a biguanide molecule by a picolate or a quinaldinate ion has little effect on the ligand field splitting and hence, perhaps, the substitution takes place easily. A slightly smaller value of $10Dq$ for the quinaldinato-complex, as compared with that for the picolinate-complex, may be ascribed to the increased resonance in the heteroligand.

TABLE II

Complex	λ_{max}	$10Dq$ in cm^{-1}	e_{max}
1. $[\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]^{3+}$	575 $\text{m}\mu$	17,400	15 ⁽¹⁰⁾
2. $[\text{CrCl}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]^+$	635 $\text{m}\mu$	15,748	24 ⁽¹¹⁾
3. $[\text{Cr}(\text{en})_3]\text{Cl}_3$	456 $\text{m}\mu$	21,930	76
4. $[\text{Cr}(\text{BigH}^+)_3]\text{Cl}_3$	482 $\text{m}\mu$	20,747	$\begin{cases} 102 \\ 103^{(11a)} \\ 84 \end{cases}$
5. $[\text{Cr}(\text{BigH}^+)_2 \text{pic}']\text{Cl}_2$	480 $\text{m}\mu$	20,833	
6. $[\text{Cr}(\text{BigH}^+)_2 \text{quinald}'](\text{ClO}_4)_2$	492 $\text{m}\mu$	20,325	93

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EXPERIMENTAL

Tris(biguanidinium) chromium(III) sulphate was prepared by the method described in the literature¹.

α-Picolinatobis(biguanidinium) chromium(III) sulphate: A suspension of tris(biguanidinium) chromium(III) sulphate in water was heated on a steam bath with an aqueous solution of *α*-picolinic acid containing a little more than the calculated amount of the acid. The orange yellow solid gradually dissolved with the separation of sparingly soluble reddish brown crystals. It was then removed from the steam bath and the solid was filtered off, washed thoroughly with hot water, alcohol and ether and dried in air.

α-Picolinatobis(biguanidinium) chromium(III) chloride: The chloride was obtained as chocolate brown crystals from the sulphate by metathesis with barium chloride.

TABLE III

Analyses of Compounds

Complex	% Cr		% N		% anion		% H ₂ O	
	Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.
1. X SO ₄ .2H ₂ O	10.11	10.23	30.15	30.31	18.72	18.89	7.00	7.09
2. X Cl ₂ .3H ₂ O	10.32	10.37	31.03	30.74	13.95	14.14	11.23 (140°)	10.78
3. X Br ₂ .1.5H ₂ O	9.22	9.23	27.84	27.36	28.19	28.38	4.61 (110°)	4.80
4. X I ₂ .2.5H ₂ O	7.75	7.70	—	—	37.56	37.59	— (120°)	—
5. X (NO ₃) ₂ .6H ₂ O	8.30	8.55	29.56	29.93	—	—	—	—
6. X (ClO ₄) ₂	9.15	9.04	26.35	26.78	—	—	—	—
7. X S ₂ O ₃ .3.5H ₂ O	9.44	9.43	27.87	27.94	20.45	20.33	—	—
8. X C ₂ O ₄ .6H ₂ O	9.25	9.08	—	—	15.00	15.38	—	—
9. X (C.S.) ₂ .5H ₂ O	5.41	5.60	16.58	16.58	—	—	—	—
10. Y SO ₄ .1.5H ₂ O	9.51	9.47	28.25	28.04	17.37	17.48	—	—
11. Y Cl ₂ .4H ₂ O	9.10	9.13	—	—	12.25	12.45	—	—
12. Y (NO ₃) ₂ .2H ₂ O	8.87	8.87	31.56	31.22	—	—	—	—
13. Y (ClO ₄) ₂ .H ₂ O	8.16	8.08	23.92	23.95	—	—	—	—

X = [Cr(BigH⁺)₂ pic⁻]

Y = [Cr(BigH⁺)₂ quinald⁻]

Other salts of the picolinato series: The bromide (chocolate brown), iodide (chocolate brown) and nitrate (pink) of the complex were prepared by mixing a concentrated solution of the potassium salts of these anions with that of complex chloride and cooling in a refrigerator.

Thiosulphate, *oxalate*, and *perchlorate* were obtained as pink solids by the action of sodium salts of these anions on the complex chloride. Except the thiosulphate, which was only sparingly soluble in hot water, they were recrystallised from water; on recrystallisation the colour deepened to chocolate brown in the case of oxalate and to red in the perchlorate.

D-Camphor-10-sulphonate (abbreviated as C.S.) of the complex was prepared by triturating the complex sulphate with a solution of the barium salt of d-camphor-10-sulphonic acid, prepared by treating the acid with an excess of barium carbonate and filtering off the unreacted carbonate. No resolution into diastereoisomers could be observed during the crystallisation of the complex camphor sulphonate.

Quinaldinatobis(biguanidinium) chromium(III) salts: The complex *sulphate*, in dirty mauve coloured crystals, was prepared in the same manner as in the case of the picolinate series. This, on metathetic reaction with barium chloride, gave the *chloride* (light maroon) of the complex, from an aqueous solution of which the *nitrate* and the *perchlorate* separated as dirty maroon coloured solid by the action of concentrated solutions of potassium nitrate and sodium perchlorate respectively. These were recrystallised from water.

Conductivity measurements were made with WTW Conductivity Meter, Type LBR. For M/1000 solutions of both $[\text{Cr}(\text{BigH}^+)_2 \text{pic}']\text{Cl}_2$ and $[\text{Cr}(\text{BigH}^+)_2 \text{quinald}'](\text{ClO}_4)_2$, $\lambda_v = 125.2 \text{ ohm}^{-1} \text{ cm}^2$, from which λ_∞ was calculated to be equal to $132.9 \text{ ohm}^{-1} \text{ cm}^2$, using Walden's formula $\lambda_\infty = \lambda_v (1 + n_1 n_2 \cdot 0.692 \nu^{-1})$, where n_1 and n_2 are the valence charges of the cation and the anion. Molar conductance works out to be $265.8 \text{ ohm}^{-1} \text{ cm}^2$ for both the species which is characteristic of a 2 : 1 electrolyte.

Magnetic moments were determined on a Gouy magnetic balance making the diamagnetic corrections using Pascal's constants¹². Values have been reported in Table I.

The electronic absorption spectra were recorded on Hilger and Watts Uvispek Photoelectric Spectrophotometer H 700 with matched 1 cm. cells. The important points are mentioned in Table II.

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